

STUDENT VOICE: THE STUDENT GUIDE

As a department, we value your 'student voice'. This means that we take on board your individual views, and the views of our students as a group. There are many ways your views might be gathered:

- Formally, in preparation for Student Voice Meetings, or by the feedback you provide on your modules, or by way of projects that are set up to work with students on a new initiative; or
- Informally, by way of discussions in class or elsewhere.

This guide explains your formal opportunities to give feedback about your modules and to tell us your views about broader issues for discussion at Student Voice Meetings. It also explains how your feedback is used.

When you take the time to provide feedback, you can expect us to:

Listen to your views about your modules and departmental matters, and use them to improve our practice.

Ensure the services that support your learning experience are aware of your needs and your views.

Respond to you. Where we can make changes, we will. Where we don't, we will explain why.

Module Evaluation and Feedback

Your views on the modules you study are important to us. We'll ask you how your module is going in the middle of the module (the Termly Review) and at the end of the module (the Module Evaluation Questionnaire). Making time in sessions to do this is important - it makes sure we're having a conversation about your feedback.

Termly Review

WHY?

To share the good practice you identify, and act on improvements you suggest (where possible) whilst you are studying the module.

WHAT?

You give feedback via your mobile at the start of a session (we leave the link open for a week)

Module team considers all responses, discusses with student reps where relevant, and responds within two teaching weeks.

THEN WHAT?

The response will be discussed at the start of a live session and saved online and on Teams.

Module Evaluation

WHY?

To make sure we consider your views and experiences when the module is updated

WHAT?

You give feedback via your mobile at the start of a session (we leave the link open for a week)

Module team considers all responses, discusses with student reps where relevant, and takes on board when updating module.

THEN WHAT?

To see the changes made to a module you previously studied, you can access a document containing all amendments to modules on the department's Moodle site, in the Student Voice tile.

Module feedback: things to think about

1. Don't confuse popularity with good teaching! Module feedback is about how well you feel you are being **supported** by your tutor – are they clear, supportive, do they give useful feedback?
2. Think about **celebrating success stories!** What does the tutor do that supports your learning that you'd like to see in other modules? If we know, we can look at doing this in other modules.
3. Be **honest and open**, but please be **respectful**, even when giving constructive criticism.
4. Where there is something you don't like, **can you explain why?** It might help to think about what you are

being taught and why it is being taught that way (if in doubt, ask your lecturer!). If you can explain to us what it is about a teaching technique that you don't like, we are in a better position to change it or provide further support. (so, for example, 'group work makes me anxious because I'm nervous about working with other students' is much more helpful than 'I don't like group work').

Where feedback doesn't result in the change you want, **we'll explain why** - e.g. some techniques that you might not be keen on are used to help prepare you for work, like presentations. Don't be disheartened, we might still be able to make your experience of this technique better from your explanations about why you don't like something.

Student Voice Meetings (SVM)

WHY?

So you can tell us what you think about the wider university environment, for example resources such as the Careers Service, the Library, pastoral support, technology

WHAT?

Each term, you give your views via mobile during class time

All comments are collated and responded to in writing by relevant staff members.

Student reps consider the comments and the responses before the SVM

THEN WHAT?

Student reps and staff attend the SVM: it is a forum for celebrating and disseminating good practice and co-creating solutions to any perceived issues (all recorded in a Rolling Action Plan).

AND THEN...

The Rolling Action Plan is shared by the SVM chair in a live lecture or via recording, and placed online and on Teams.

A document with every comment and every response is saved online and on Teams, so you can see the individual response to any comments you made.

AND FINALLY...

The Rolling Action Plan is considered during every subsequent SVM to ensure the agreed actions are carried out in the required timeframe by the relevant person.

SVM feedback: things to think about

1. SVM feedback is about your **wider experience** at university. It isn't the place to comment on **individual lecturers** or **individual modules**. These issues should be raised in the Termly Review/MEQ.
 2. Comments regarding **themes** that run across modules e.g. approaches to assessment, timetables etc can be raised in the SVM.
 3. Be **honest and open**, but please be **respectful!**
 4. Please provide **positive comments** as well as areas for improvement. We are keen to share **good practice!**
 5. Where feedback doesn't result in a change, **we'll explain why** - e.g. some issues may be outside the department's control. Don't be disheartened – we will always pass matters outside of our control to the relevant department and will always be open to having a conversation with you about why changes have not been made.
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